

Water purification and storage hardware

prepared for

WP3.3– Water Purification and Storage

Version: 0.1

Published:

Approved by: Giorgio Boscheri TAS Work Package Leader

Approved by: Paul Zabel DLR Project Leader

List of Authors:

Participant No.	Short name	Author name(s)
6	TAS	Rachele Perelli

Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
0.1	01.02.2024	Rachele Perelli	First issue

Table of contents

Table of contents	3
1 Introduction	4
1.1 Applicable Documents.....	4
1.2 Reference Documents	4
1.3 Acronyms.....	4
2 LUWEX WPS HW Delivery Data	5
3 Acceptance and Functional Tests status.....	9

1 Introduction

This document, deliverable D3.5 for LUWEX project, describes the water purification and storage subsystem hardware present in TAS-I and that will be integrated in LUWEX system at TUBS premises.

1.1 Applicable Documents

[AD1] LUWEX-LSG-WP2.1-D2.1-System Requirements Document_v1.0

1.2 Reference Documents

[RD1] LUWEX-DLR-WP2.3-D2.3-Preliminary Design Report-v1.0

[RD2] LUWEX-TAS-WP3.3-D3.4 WPS design report

1.3 Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
BBM	Breadboard Model
HW	Hardware
LIBS	Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy
MF	Microfiltration
PWR	Politechnika Wroclawska
RO	Reverse Osmosis
SWY	Scanway
TAS-I	Thales Alenia Space Italia
TUBS	Technische Universität Braunschweig
TVAC	Thermal Vacuum chamber
WECS	Water Extraction and Capturing subsystem
WPS	Water Purification and Storage subsystem
WUST	Wroclaw University of Science and Technology

2 LUXWEX WPS HW Delivery Data

The LUXWEX WPS BBM deliverable HW (designed according to [RD2]) is composed of the elements in Table 1. HW status is described in the last column of Table 1.

Table 1 – WPS BB Deliverable HW status

Element/Component	Qty	Manufacturer	Part Number	HW Status
Reservoirs				
Raw water tank (2L)	1	DURAN	PIREX 2l	Available at TAS-I Torino
Clean water tank (2L)	1	DURAN	PIREX 2l	Available at TAS-I Torino
Waste water tank (0.5L)	1	DURAN	PIREX 0,5l	Available at TAS-I Torino
Water treatment				
Microfiltration unit	1	Sartorius	Maxicap 10"	Available at TAS-I Torino
Reverse osmosis unit	1	DUPONT	Filmtech Aqualast 1812 HR	Available at TAS-I Torino
Activated carbon unit	1	CAMEL	Actisorb MJ	Available at TAS-I Torino
Ion exchange resin unit	1	DUPONT	AmberTec UP6040 H/OH	Available at TAS-I Torino
Sensors and Controllers/Drivers				
Flowmeter	2	IFM	SM6020	Available at TAS-I Torino
small flows adaptor	1	IFM	E40129	Available at TAS-I Torino
Pressure sensor	5	IFM	PT5404	Available at TAS-I Torino
Conductivity probe	2	IFM	LDL101	Available at TAS-I Torino
Water tank level sensor (scale)	2	PIECO	load cell + controller 0-4 kg	Available at TAS-I Torino
Temperature indicator	1	IFM	TA2105	Available at TAS-I Torino
Fluidic lines				
RO pump (centrifugal)	1	Fluid-o-Tech	GA serie	Available at TAS-I Torino
RO Pump Driver	1	Moon's	BLD10-A-S	Available at TAS-I Torino
Microfiltration pump	1	Marco Fluidtech	16404113 - UPX-C	Available at TAS-I Torino
WECS to WPS pump (peristaltic)	1	Etatron	B3V-1201	Available at TAS-I Torino
WPS to SWY LIBS and PWR	1	Etatron	B3V-1201	Available at TAS-I Torino
Non Return Valves	2	John Guest	1/4SCV	Available at TAS-I Torino
Regulation valve (needle)	1	Fluidfit		Available at TAS-I Torino
3 ways 2 positions solenoid valve	1	JP Fluid Control	TP-DA014S040F-024DC	Available at TAS-I Torino
Piping set	1	Fluidfit		Available at TAS-I Torino
Sampling port	5	Fluidfit		Available at TAS-I Torino
Union Tee for Sampling ports	5	Fluidfit		Available at TAS-I Torino
Inlet QD fitting male	1	Hamlet	QC4SSDL1/4	Available at TAS-I Torino
Inlet QD fitting female	1	Hamlet	QC4SSBLB1/4	Available at TAS-I Torino

QD fittings in line male	8	CPC	PLCD29004	Available at TAS-I Torino
QD fittings in line female	8	CPC	PLCD11004	Available at TAS-I Torino
Inlet I/F to + Outlet I/F from T001 male	2	CPC	PLCD29004	Available at TAS-I Torino
Inlet I/F to + Outlet I/F from T001 female panel mounted	2	CPC	PLCD11004	Available at TAS-I Torino
Inlet I/F to T002 male	1	CPC	PLCD29004	Available at TAS-I Torino
Inlet I/F to T002 female panel mounted	1	CPC	PLCD11004	Available at TAS-I Torino
Inlet I/F to + Outlet I/F from T003 male	2	CPC	PLCD29004	Available at TAS-I Torino
Inlet I/F to + Outlet from T003 female panel mounted	2	CPC	PLCD11004	Available at TAS-I Torino
Vacuum relief valves	3	hole	hole	Available at TAS-I Torino
Structure				
Mounting plate	1			Available at TAS-I Torino
Mounting brackets (1 set), handles (3x)	1			Available at TAS-I Torino
Electrical Connectors				
Circular MIL STD D38999 female, panel mounted electric connector 41 pins	1	Souriau	8D021W41SN-LC	Available at TAS-I Torino
Circular MIL STD D38999 female, panel mounted electric connector 26 pins	1	Souriau	8D017W26SN-LC	Available at TAS-I Torino
Spares				
3m jumpers 1/4" with CPC connectors	2			Available at TAS-I Torino
3m jumpers 1/4" with CPC connector and Hamlet connector	1			Available at TAS-I Torino
Reverse osmosis unit	1	DUPONT	Filmtech Aqualast 1812 HR	Available at TAS-I Torino
Activated carbon, 1.2kg	1	CAMEL	Actisorb MJ	Available at TAS-I Torino
Ion Exchange Resins, 1.75kg	1	DUPONT	AmberTec UP6040 H/OH	Available at TAS-I Torino

WPS subsystem HW is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 below:

Figure 1 – WPS HW frontal view

Figure 2 – WPs HW Top view

The WPS subsystem HW is assembled, tested at subsystem level and available in TAS-I Torino. WPS Subsystem HW is ready for delivery to TUBS and will be delivered for integration according to LUXEX project schedule.

3 Acceptance and Functional Tests status

Test ID	Test Title	Affected Requirements as per [AD1]	Test Status
EGSE Acceptance Tests			
E01	Electrical continuity + Pin function verification.	-	Test Accomplished
E02	Components bench test	-	Test Accomplished
WPS Subsystem Acceptance Tests			
A01	Pin function verification.	Test Added	Test Accomplished
A02	Mass and envelope verification.	▪ 1.5.2.	Test Accomplished
A03	Leak check and flowrate verification.	▪ 2.4.4, 2.4.7.	Test Accomplished
WPS Subsystem Functional verification tests			
F01	Outlet water parameters monitoring.	▪ 1.6.2, 1.6.3, 2.4.6, 2.4.10 (*)	Test Accomplished